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ATMO-ACCESS Meeting 22-23 June 2022

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Time	22/06/22	23/06/22
9:00 - 10:00	WP5 meeting (Alex Vermulen / Cathrine Lund Myhre)	WP2 meeting (Iwona Stachlewska)
10:00 - 11:00		WP4 meeting (Stefan Reimann)
11:00 - 12:00		
12:00-13:00	Lunch	Lunch
13:00-14:00		General Assembly
14:00-15:00	WP6 meeting (John Wenger)	TNA Q&A session
15:00 - 16:00		

WP5 Meeting

Task 5.1 is presented by Richard Rud and 5.2 is by Alex Vermeulen.

Several questions are asked by the participants.

Gordon M.: Is this service replicating the functionality of FLEXPART and STILT that are available anyway? Are there any additional functionalities being added? Alex V. replies that indeed they built up on the existing services but making them more user-friendly and usable from people outside the RIs.

Sabine P.: What are the different limitations of the RIs? What about the central access point?

Richard R.: The services are open, and everyone is free to use them, the homeless data portal routes the requests to the respective RIs where individual workflows are triggered. There is no limitation, but the requests are not offered for all types of data.

Alex V.: We need decisions to reply to this question. If we decide to develop a common interface, we can agree on standards, we can use integration tools offered by ENVRIFAIR. In terms of workload, having a common interface would be the best option of course and we could develop it. Having one would save up costs, on the other side it would be very complex, and it might produce instabilities on the backend (if this is changed, then the whole interface would be impacted). We could indicate the limitations at an early stage, to make it easy and not confusing for the users.

Damien B.: We have previously decided to offer preprocessed results which are already prepared. If we decide to also do new developments, it would be difficult for IAGOS to find the resources. The point is confirmed Valérie T. and by Cathrine L. Valérie T. suggests an alternative solution of such development through the use of the homeless data service.

Markus F. reminds to always take a user perspective: offering precalculated results is more user friendly, while for the footprint there are not many potential users.

Sabine P.: We have to put a limit to customize service, otherwise it is too costly. We should focus on virtual access, if the data is precalculated (or already available data), we can accept it. Alex V. agrees but underlines that the project's text says otherwise. Paolo L. interprets the texts in a way for which the project needs to find solutions for sustainable services but does not necessarily need to implement them.

Cathrine L.: Is it important to have a common login to all platforms? Alex V. suggests a unique ID generator for the users to use on all ATMO-ACCESS platforms, for all virtual access. It is

confirmed by the Coordination, as VA rules clearly indicate the need to track users who access virtual services. It is up to the project to find a way to do that. Users can see the services' description without logging in but they need to register to use them.

Task 5.3

Damien B. presents the task.

Sabine P. asks whether there will be any constraints once the service is launched. Damien B. indicates that maybe the datasets to be made available could be one potential limitation. It will depend on each RI. And if these datasets are very different, and do not follow the standards, then we may not be able to manage all of them.

Paolo L. asks to clarify whether the plan is to use the databases from the 3 RIs for this service.

Sabine P.: Have you thought about a user helpdesk? Damien B. confirms that one will be put in place.

What about the collection of user feedback? Ideas could be taken from WP10, which has foreseen it. Paolo L. asks to establish a link with WP2, to collect the feedback.

Sabine P. does not see any conflict in these services, with the VA standard procedure. In principle, access is already free and open from the RIs. It can not be limited to a restricted number of users.

Concerning the evaluation of access requests, Gordon M. states that it would be useful to know the terms of reference before starting the evaluation. And eventually amend the access accordingly.

It is decided to have **one continuous call (or rather an announcement) to be launched in spring and which will need corresponding communication and publicity so that users need to know what is available.**

About the establishment of an assessment panel: it is suggested to benefit from and base it on the current User Panel which is composed of around 6 or 7 users, who were invited to give feedback, specifically for tasks 5.1 and 5.3.

A (physical) WP5 workshop is planned in August/September 2022 with task leaders, RI developers and ATMO Coordination to discuss the central VA portal and entry point, common request forms and interface/service switchboard to the different services located at the RIs.

Timeline:

- WP5 workshop (Aug/Sep 2022)
- Overall architecture design (Oct 2022)
- Prototype services (Feb 2023)
- User evaluation (Mar 2023)
- Announcement / launch for VA (Mar 2023)
- Basic 5.3 and 5.1 services are available, but not all functionalities (Apr 2023)
- Services are operational (Jun 2023)

Paolo L. reminds the need to stick as much as possible to the original timeline and to avoid any possible delays.

Gordon M. asks about the need to include SAMU. If an applicant for VA asks for too much access, then there is a need to iterate between the provider and the users, should this be done through SAMU, or can the "limits" be defined in advance so as to avoid these situations? It is agreed that there will be no need to include WP9, interactions will be handled within WP5 and WP10.

WP6 meeting

John W. introduces the WP and plans for Tasks 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4.

Task 6.2 New Access Modalities for International Stakeholders

Doina N. presents the timeline and features (codesign, 2-step application) for this pilot, implying tailored services which will be implemented/offered through different types of cross-RI facilities including mobile platforms and central laboratories. The pilot targets space agencies and similar programmes supporting Cal/Val activities of satellite missions, with a focus on EarthCARE which is scheduled for launch in October 2023 and requiring pre-launch Cal/Val activities. The TNA pilot process involves a 2-step application, with the 1st pilot to be launched as soon as possible, and includes the submission of an initial concept note which will be evaluated by an independent panel based on scientific relevance and feasibility. A co-design phase will follow in a 2nd stage and is expected to involve the selected applicants to define the work plan and technical details.

Paolo L. suggests restricting to EARTHcare for testing the process and opening it later on, we design a call based on the capacity and then the providers respond. The competition will be in the network design maybe with help from ESA in the panel and we'll be selecting facilities based on specific criteria for which we have the pre-launch phase.

Next steps:

- Stakeholders to submit a proposal of interest not using PASS but offline document
 - Doina N. to propose a template
- open the call mid-July and close it in September (in accordance with WP7)
- Paolo L. suggests making an ad-hoc panel (external reviewers) on this specific call.

Task 6.3 New Access Modalities for innovators

4 proposals for new innovative access from industry were exposed:

- urban measurements (Green deal projects RI URBAN and PAUL)
- intercomparison (focus on instrument testing with new/advanced measurements techniques at CL and particularly mobile platforms/)
- access to harmonized and optimized testing procedures (ATMO-TECH related, evaluation of proposal submitted to HORIZON-INFRA-2022-TECH-01 is ongoing)
- access to ATMO-box for low-cost measurements of GHG and air quality.

Next steps are:

- Organising 2 codesign seminars (offer & need matching) + questionnaire for manufacturer intent for participation
- Identifying lead CL for the intercomp (and lead CL) (summer/early fall)
- Describing the intercomp exercise and access (end of 2022)
- Establishing a link with WP4 training C2 miniaturized sensors and drones. ATMO-BOXes could be included in the sensor training planned in 2023.

Gordon M. and Sabine P. suggested the idea of continuous calls targeted to the private sector, supplemented by the codesign elements. The current (second) call for TNA is already aimed at Green Deal projects. A continuous call also requires targeted communication towards the private sector. Chambers are particularly encouraged to join the pilot,

Task 6.4 New Access Modalities for public authorities

A first WG meeting was organised on 16 June and was attended by 23 participants but only 2 stakeholders representing Greek public authorities. We should mobilize participants for the next meeting in September.

- possible to involve more people via existing networks. Paolo L suggests using Green deal projects as a way of communicating towards public authorities. ATMO ACCESS could propose a post campaign activity after RI Urbans and PAUL campaigns. Andres A./CSIC has contacts in Barcelona but feels that the limiting factor is the transnational aspect as interest of public authorities is on local, regional or national level.
- need an RI Urbans point of contact to promote TNA options and initiate a co-design
- targeted communication effort to have involvement in the WG: it has to go through partners, centralised communication is very limited.
- not an issue to wait for a while to see how it goes forward: assess public authorities needs in terms of remote access to data, NRT data access. Possibilities could also come from mobile platforms or training.

WP2 meeting

Iwona S. gives an overview of WP2 activities.

Possible improvements foreseen:

- To have an integrated communication strategy between the 3 RIs, regular meetings should be organised, notably prior to calls launch including brainstorming activities.
 - TNA Feedback questionnaire includes questions about communication channels and assessments.
- Need more information coming from the other WPs about the different calls and their targets. WP2 should attend other WP meetings. For instance: tutorials are linked to WP4, 9, 10.
- Specific conferences require specific communication material. There is a multi channel way of doing so.

Important to assess the effectiveness of comms actions towards all the 3 communities

The 3 RI communication officers add:

Giulia S.: it is indeed useful to have regular meetings to act and react to upcoming calls. Brainstorming will be welcomed. If there are new opportunities, we need to plan in advance and share the work.

Hannah C. states that to her, it is not so clear where the IAGOS community fits with the access strategy.

Katri A.: It is possible for ICOS to advertise ATMO at ICOS science conference (through flyers).

Matilde O. identifies 2 actions:

1. Communication needs to be done separately by each RI through their specific channels
2. Communication actions and material needs to be prepared commonly by the 3 RIs and UW since there is no specific partner nor RI in charge of it. So, work needs to be shared.

→ **work to be shared among the 3RI + PO + UW, since there is no one dedicated to it.**

Paolo L. reminds that PMs could be used to have a communication activity somewhere not necessarily a scientist, someone who could connect the 3 comms officers. He invites the 3 RIs and the WP leader to make sure to have the means (HR) to do the work.

WP4 meeting

Hartmut H. presented the detailed results from the report related to existing physical access training and Diego B. the results from the report related to existing remote access training received from the questionnaires sent to ACTRIS/ICOS/IAGOS on past training activities.

- some information are missing for CL/DC training, it will be incorporated in the final version of the report.
- Combined access (PA+RA) could be very useful and offer new opportunities for training: innovative training is important: remote access offers transition to more exploitation of our training potential.

Virtual training

Antonia Z. presented the planned MOOC concept. IMT has some licenses for the MOOC for the project but in the long term it could be hosted by the DC.

- access will be done through ATMO website then MOOC landing page.
- Define the users targets in advance to make it the most useful as possible. The focus is on young scientists. Maybe it could be more tailored to specific user groups in the future and also used as a teaser for the annual ACTRIS training school.
- It is suggested to make a connection with the private sector to show how instruments could be tested, or to have them as teachers in the MOOC
- After the 2 week MOOC, the videos should be available as passive resource material.
- Timing is to have it ready by the end of 2022.

Cross RI training pilots

- Training at AGORA (planned in June 2023) will be hybrid and involve physical and remote participants, and it is planned to make recordings available for VA access. Training will involve lectures, hands-on in-situ and remote sensing measurements including work in the laboratory and data analysis.
- Training at NAOK (2023/24): remote access possibilities should be foreseen. It is planned to encourage new users in connection with the EIRENE RI (linking environment and human health).
- Training at USRL using drones and at CIGAS-CH for sensor testing are planned as hybrid activities for physical and remote access

Call schedule

Specific calls will be organized for the above training pilots. Other training opportunities will be included within the general call schedule, e.g., in connection with the Green Deal projects, access to CL etc.

All actors involved should know what is planned in time. From a user perspective too many calls could be confusing

Rosa: close interaction is needed to prepare specific form for these training forms and need to reflect on evaluation of these applications.

More discussions needed with wp10 to define VA.

A remote access workshop is planned in December 2023 to further promote and develop the remote access opportunities (not only related to training)

- invite other RIs (EMBRC, Instruct ERIC) to share experiences notably in pricing about the remote access (WP1), global companies could share experiences-> **WP4 will take the lead in the organisation.**

General Assembly

The second ATMO-ACCESS General Assembly took place virtually on June 23rd.

The Meeting convened at 13:00 PM CEST and was chaired by the co-coordinator Sabine Pilippin.

Agenda:

1. Introduction and quorum
2. 1st GA minutes – for approval
3. Project updates
4. Access Evaluation Panel (AEP) – for approval
5. ATMO-ACCESS New SAB member – for approval
6. Planned call for new platforms
7. 1st Periodic Reporting
8. Expected 1st amendment to Grant Agreement
9. AOB

1. Quorum

32 partners are present (see list in Annex II). Thus, Quorum is achieved, and the GA is legally effective.

2. 1st GA minutes – for approval

The minutes from ATMO-ACCESS 1st GA were approved unanimously.

3. Project updates

A short update on WP main advancements and bottlenecks is presented by the project Coordinator (Paolo Laj). The interconnection of WP with the project is underlined. The status/progress/issues of each WP is shortly summarized.

Regarding project management, intranet, web portal and carbon footprint are presented. Cathrine Lund Myhre (NILU) asks to send regular reminders on the footprint to WP leaders to fill in the table.

A few reactions regarding the organisation of TNA were noted, notably:

Doina Nicolae (INOE): the high success rate can be explained by the fact that applications are codesigned with the access providers, and this raises their quality. She also adds that a high success rate is expected at the beginning of the project and since no TNA has been available since 2019. It is suggested to add a KPI about user inquiry to the access providers

Leonard Rivier (CEA) adds that some calls are not resource limited but user limited (e.g. private sector).

Gordon McFiggans (UMAN) asks if there is a clear guidance from the commission on which values the calculated success rate uses - i.e. does it need to relate to success at peer-reviewed evaluation? In which case, co-design will not mitigate a high success rate.

4. Access Evaluation Panel (AEP) – for approval

The procedure for appointing [Access Evaluation Panel](#) members were presented and approved without any objections.

5. ATMO-ACCESS New Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) member – for approval

The replacement of Minna Vakeva by Aki Pajunoja (new CEO of Airmodus) as member of the SAB was approved without any objections.

6. Planned call for new platforms

The call for new platforms and criteria for applying are presented, especially the capacity to host users and tracked costs of the past 2 years.

- Stéphane Sauvage: Are new potential platforms only observation/exploratory platforms? or could it be a new central lab unit?
- Access will not be granted to National facilities in the frame of ATMO-ACCESS. The new site must reply to external user demand.

7. 1st Periodic Report

The 1st ATMO-ACCESS reporting period ends in September 2022: RP1 month 1 – month 18 (1.4.2021 - 30.9.2022)

Periodic reports (both technical and financial) are due up to 60 days after the end of the reporting period, i.e. by November 30th, 2022.

Information on the reports is given as well as the main deadlines:

- Technical Report: first draft to be ready by September 23rd, and final deadline October 15th.
- Financial report: first draft to be ready by October 17th, and final deadline by October 28th.

8. Expected 1st amendment to the Grant Agreement

Planned amendments were presented to the GA.

- A request for a 1st amendment to the Grant Agreement will be made in the coming months. This request is in relation to the transfer TNA reserve budget (325 k€) at CNR to CNRS to allow centralized redistribution to new TNA platforms (access + T&S budget). No impact on other partners expected. The procedure for GA approval for the amendment request is expected via written procedure and to be agreed by the majority of the GA members.
- We expect another amendment at the beginning of 2023 for the addition of new platforms and TNA.

Beneficiaries are asked to inform the project office (by email) for any needs for amendment as soon as possible.

9. AOB

Calendar of the upcoming meetings is presented.

For the next GA 2023 planned 29-31 March 2023, suggestions of locations are welcome from the consortium. Preference will be given to central European locations.

The meeting finishes at 14:05.

TNA Q&A session

A TNA discussion session is organized with all TA-VA access providers:

- Overview of planned call schedule with ATMO
- Results and metrics of 1st TNA
- Timeline & selection process for 2nd call
- Tailored evaluation form for reviewers
- Use of PASS platform

The overall timeline of planned calls and access periods until the end of the project is presented. A selection meeting by an internal panel is planned at the end of each 3-stage evaluation period. This proposition will help WP2 & 9 to progress more smoothly. Too many calls open at the same time could be confusing for users. Doina N. specifies that the call for international stakeholders will be launched on July 15th.

Martial H. : could the evaluation of a project start at project submission? Rosa P. replies that for the 1st call, applications were evaluated as they were submitted. For the 2nd call it will partially change as the call itself is evaluated at the end of the call by STVB which will establish a short list in proposal.

Martial H. underlines that, despite understanding the calendar and need for success rate, in Paris there will be a comprehensive PANAME field campaign. ATMO calendar is really unfortunate as it does not allow to provide access during such campaign. Could field campaigns be considered in fast track call? Lucia M. and Leonard R. support this suggestion. Doina N. agrees that campaigns are opportunities and should be listed under the fast track. Coordinators reply that fast track is limited to unexpected events only and field campaigns may be well planned ahead of time. The frequent recurrent calls should allow better planning of participating via TNA in future field campaigns.

Paolo L. stresses the fact that fast-track TNAs are for unexpected events (natural disasters...) and can therefore bypass the evaluation.

Doina N.: In the project we are optimizing the TNA process, optimizing interaction with users, reduce workload on providers and SAMU side. How can we make sure these resources are wisely spent to be sufficient for all the calls? International stakeholder pilot requires a lot of resources from facilities.

Paolo L.: at the end of evaluation process a committee takes the final decision, keeping in mind how much is being spent on each call (to make sure there is funding left for the last call).

Paolo L. also stresses that reducing the evaluation period to 2 months requires reactivity from access providers. So far, this has not always been the case, and it has slowed down evaluations.

Léonard R. asks if the SAMU evaluation of the use of resources can be made available somewhere. Giuseppe G.: it should be, but it really depends on the timely provision of accurate information by providers, otherwise it will always be outdated.

Rosa P. presented the results from 1st TNA call:

- 75 applications received, 237 users, 63 accepted, 2 banned, 3 rejected, 7 reviews ongoing. 12 TNA completed so far.
- 275 331€ in travels and subsistence asked, 123 434€ decided
- Almost half facilities asked are observational platforms (36/75)
- 50% of physical access, 21% remote and 29% combination of both
- 13 users from private sector, 224 from public sector
- 90 internal / 147 external users to the project

→ **WP7 will need this information and statistics, to be made available by SAMU.**

It is reminded that TNA money isn't guaranteed to any of the beneficiaries, a reallocation may be done throughout the project.

Leonard R. asked for more details about the share between ICOS and ACTRIS platforms. Some facilities are a combination of ACTRIS and ICOS. The important thing is the content of the proposal rather than the site. It is important to have this information per RI, to understand potential very different access dynamics between RIs and see if this needs particular action or not.

Cathrine L. agrees with Léonard R. and adds that for the homeless data portal it would be useful to have more information on instruments/data.

→ **Sabine P. suggests adding a simple table in ATMO-CONNECT for Access Providers to know the # of access provider vs planned.**

→ **SAMU to add metrics about proposals per RI.**

2nd call timeline:

- 06.05.2022 - 06.07-2022: 2nd call open
- 06.07.2022 - 13.07.2022: Feasibility check
- 13.07.2022 - 12.09.2022: Review

- 19.09.2022: Final list of accepted TNAs
- October 2022 - October 2023: Access period

The PASS platform will be used for feasibility review and confirmation of access

→ It is reminded to providers to always consider a deputy, in order to stay with the time schedule.

Next steps:

- **SAMU will pre-register providers' accounts in the platform and send invitations to complete the registration (June 27th)**
- **Providers have to complete account registration (July 1st)**
- **SAMU will complete eligibility of the first group of applications submitted to date and notifies providers to start the feasibility check (July 1st)**
- Providers can start feasibility reviews
- **SAMU completes eligibility of the last group of applications submitted in the last days and notifies providers to start the feasibility (July 8st)**
- **Providers complete all the feasibility reviews (by July 13th)**

Paolo Prati asked to consider (and make clear to the applicants) flexibility in the percentage of co-financing of T&S costs from the provider.

Rosa P. summarizes the main news compared to the 1st call (besides the platform):

- More rigid timeline
- Plan B in case of delays/no answers from providers (rejection) or reviewers (review from an internal panel)
- Cross review of final list of accepted TNA by Coordination-WP7-WP9

The next TNA PI meeting will be on December 7th 2022.

ANNEX I

Participants of WP5 meeting

Affiliation:	Name:
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ANNEX II

Participants of the GA

Affiliation:	Name:	Partner representative in the GA (32 out of 38 present)
UGR	Alados-Arboledas Lucas	X
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UCA	Baray Jean-Luc	
UAIC	Bejan Iustinian	
PSI	Bell David	
UEvora	Bortoli Daniele	X
NOA	Bougiatioti Katerina	
UPC	Comeron Adolfo	
TAU	Dal Maso Miikka	X
UGR	Bermejo Diego	
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NILU	Fiebig Markus	
CNR	Gagliardi Simone	
CNR	Gargano Giuseppe	
PSI	Gysel-Beer Martin	X
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FMI	Hyvärinen Antti	
ČHMÚ	Išták Tomáš	
UW	Janicka Lucja	
BUW	Klotz Iulia	

Affiliation:	Name:	Partner representative in the GA (32 out of 38 present)
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EULS	Krasnov Dmitrii	X
CNRS	Kretz Vincent	
CNRS Coordination	Laj Paolo	X
UHEL	Lehtipalo Katrianne	X
FMI	Leijala Ulpu	X
CEA	Leo Rivier	
NOA	Liakakou Eleni	
NILU	Lund Myhre Cathrine	X
ZAMG	Maier Christian	X
CHMI	Mbengue Saliou	
UMAN	McFiggans Gordon	X
CNRS	Mellouki Wahid	
NOA	Mihalopoulos Nikos	X
CNR	Mona Lucia	X
KIT	Möhler Ottmar	X
CEAM	Muñoz Amalia	X
INOE	Nicolae Doina	X
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JRC	Putaud Jean-Philippe	X
EMPA	Reimann Stefan	X
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ATMO ACCESS

Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

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UCC	Wenger John	X
BUW	Wiesen Peter	X
ICPF	Zdimal Vladimir	